
D6.2 / Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan

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List of abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CE	Conformité Européenne
CI/CD	Continuous integration, continuous delivery, and continuous deployment
dBM	Digital biomarker
DMP	Data management plan
EC	European Commission
EPO	European Patent Office
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability
FDA	Food and drugs administration
FHIR	Fast Health Interoperability Resources
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HCPs	Healthcare Professionals
HW	Hardware
IP	Intellectual property
IPR	Intellectual property rights
ISRCTN	International Standard Registered Clinical/social sTudy Number
KERs	Key exploitable results
KPI	Key performance indicator
MAFEIP	Monitoring and Assessment Framework for the European Innovation Partnership
MHRA	Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency
mHealth	Mobile health
ML	Machine learning
MVP	Minimum viable product
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership

PD	Parkinson's disease
R&I	Research and Innovation
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
SW	Computer Software
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

Deliverable D6.2 serves as a detailed roadmap for the AI-PROGNOSIS project's Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan, including stakeholders' analysis, language and impact evaluation.

The dissemination and communication strategy of the AI-PROGNOSIS is based on the active involvement of all consortium partners, delivering messages tailored to target audiences, using various dissemination and communication channels and tools, ensuring timely and consistent communication, creating synergies with related initiatives, and conducting regular monitoring and evaluation.

The exploitation strategy outlines the objectives and plan for leveraging the AI-PROGNOSIS project results. The primary objectives of this strategy are to ensure the commercialisation and applicability of the AI-PROGNOSIS outcomes beyond the project's duration. This includes short-term and long-term exploitation considerations, including socio-economic analysis, regulatory approval, and intellectual property management.

Through the whole project's implementation period, a series of reports will be provided as deliverables, tracking results and implemented activities. These include D6.3 "First report on project visibility and educational material" (month 18), D6.5 "Midterm report on project visibility and educational material" (month 32) and D6.6 "Final report on project visibility and educational material" at the end of the project (month 48), D6.4 "Exploitation and regulatory approval plan (initial version)" (month 22), and D6.7 "Exploitation and regulatory approval plan (final version)" (month 48).

Overall, Deliverable 6.2 provides a comprehensive framework for the AI-PROGNOSIS Dissemination, communication and exploitation activities, ensuring that the project's results are effectively disseminated, reach the intended audiences, and deliver the maximum possible impact.

1 Introduction

This document D6.2 “Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan” is the second deliverable of WP6. It falls under Task 6.1 “Dissemination and communication planning, implementation and monitoring”, which focuses on planning, implementing, and monitoring the project's dissemination and communication activities.

This document offers guidelines for various dissemination and communication activities designed to engage a wide range of stakeholders. It outlines the tools and channels to be used for dissemination and communication and highlights the planned actions aimed at achieving the exploitation of the project's results and maximising its impact.

1.1 Document scope

By ensuring the successful implementation of the pathways towards impact in the long term, the project consortium aims to establish AI-PROGNOSIS as a point of reference for the fight against Parkinson's disease (PD). This goal requires a strong brand name, dedication from all partners and effective management from the coordination team to reach and engage various stakeholders.

The purpose of this deliverable is to establish the strategic framework and provide a detailed plan for dissemination, communication and exploitation, including stakeholder analysis, language, and impact evaluation.

The Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan is designed to achieve the following objectives:

- Spread information about and promote the project, highlighting its results and innovative potential;
- Ensure that project results are widely accessible for long-term research and application; and
- Facilitate the practical utilisation and value creation of the project's outcomes.

The core priorities in the AI-PROGNOSIS Dissemination, communication and exploitation strategy are organised around three complementary actions as follows:

- **Dissemination actions;**
- **Exploitation actions; and**
- **Communication activities.**

This deliverable is part of Work Package 6 “Dissemination, communication and exploitation”, with the objective of:

- Maximising visibility of the project (outcomes) and facilitating knowledge exchange through careful planning, implementation and monitoring of dissemination, communication and networking activities;
- Developing PD-related educational content;
- Setting out a roadmap for regulatory approval of the AI-PROGNOSIS digital tools; and
- Performing a thorough socio-economic/market analysis and developing concrete joint/individual exploitation plans.

WP6 is a transversal work package integrating the results of all WPs for the dissemination, communication and exploitation process (see **Figure 1**), and aiming to ensure that the outputs

and knowledge arising from all the activities of the project are visible to the broader audience, can be learned from and implemented on a European scale.

Figure 1 Interrelation of WP6 with other WPs

WP6 activities are anchored in four central tasks, namely:

- **T6.1 Dissemination and communication planning, implementation and monitoring;**
- **T6.2 Clustering and networking activities;**
- **T6.3 PD educational content development; and**
- **T6.4 Regulatory approval and exploitation strategy.**

The activities of these tasks will ensure openness, visibility and reuse of the AI-PROGNOSIS outcomes through open science, effective dissemination/communication and strategic networking/joint activities.

T6.1 focuses on planning, conducting and monitoring all the dissemination and communication activities of the project. Additionally, this task will highlight creating an active AI-PROGNOSIS community of stakeholders, increasing the awareness and visibility of the project results.

T6.1 is closely related to T6.2, where clustering and networking activities to raise awareness, exchange knowledge and communicate the project vision and outcomes to key stakeholder groups are foreseen.

T6.3 focuses on PD educational content development to raise PD awareness and enhance health literacy, targeting persons with and without PD. To create the material, the task will work in close collaboration with the project's clinical partners.

T6.4 focuses on a regulatory approval and exploitation plan development to pave the way for the uptake of project outcomes beyond its lifetime.

Reports focusing on T6.1, T6.2 and T6.3 results and activities implemented will be provided throughout the whole project's period as deliverables D6.3 "First report on project visibility and educational material" (month 18), D6.5 "Midterm report on project visibility and education material" (month 32) and D6.6 "Final report on project visibility and education material" at the end of the project (month 48).

In collaboration with WP1's task T1.5 "Innovation and intellectual property management", a Regulatory approval and exploitation plan will be developed and exploitable outcomes of the project identified (T6.4). This will contribute to the deliverables D6.4 "Exploitation and regulatory approval plan (initial version)" (month 22), and D6.7 "Exploitation and regulatory approval plan (final version)" (month 48).

On a larger scale, the dissemination, communication and exploitation strategy depends on all WPs in disseminating results and outputs to specific stakeholders and defining exploitable outputs. Thus, active input from content-related WP partners is expected, not only through their results and deliverables but also by identifying key audiences for their results.

SMARTSOL SIA leads this task and is responsible for planning, implementation, monitoring, and coordination of activities while the rest of the partners contribute to the plan, communication/dissemination, exploitation activities and reporting.

In this manner, the aim of the AI-PROGNOSIS Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan is to promulgate findings and outputs of the project to key stakeholders to create value within the target communities and initiatives in the EU.

1.2 Document structure

This document establishes the basis for developing a common dissemination, communication and exploitation plan in the AI-PROGNOSIS project. It is intended to give an overview of the types of dissemination, exploitation and communication activities planned during the project, showcase the results of the project, and bring it to the public and the market.

The present report is organised as follows:

- The Executive summary provides a summary of the whole document.
- Section 1 introduces the main vision and scope of the AI-PROGNOSIS dissemination, exploitation and communication plan.
- Section 2 presents the AI-PROGNOSIS dissemination and communication strategy, defines the core objectives and targeted stakeholders, and outlines the overall approach. It further breaks down the specific activities and channels used for dissemination and communication, defines dissemination and communication guidelines and introduces the evaluation and monitoring of KPIs.
- Section 3 outlines the project exploitation plan and IP management, setting clear objectives for the project's exploitation efforts and defining specific strategies for transforming project outputs into exploitable products and services, including intellectual property management.
- Finally, Section 4 concludes by emphasising the significance of the dissemination, communication and exploitation plan outlined in this document. D6.2, as a strategic roadmap with clearly defined actions, aims to ensure the project's outputs are well-disseminated and effectively exploited for long-term impact.

2 Dissemination and communication strategy

2.1 Objectives

Given the nature of the AI-PROGNOSIS project, dissemination and communication activities are fundamental to raising awareness about the AI-PROGNOSIS initiative and its technology innovations, and attracting interest from potential users. To reflect this need, the dissemination and communication strategy of the project comprises activities that aim to communicate the project developments to the relevant target audiences.

The primary objectives of the dissemination and communication strategy for AI-PROGNOSIS are:

- **Disseminating scientific achievements** of the project and making the outputs widely available for research and business purposes in the long term;
- **Informing key stakeholders** about project objectives, progress, results and their innovation potential;
- **Increasing awareness and engagement of people with and at risk of PD** for addressing their issues and concerns in order to increase their awareness and build trust in new technology;
- **Reaching similar/relevant R&I projects** for promoting networking and joint activities;
- **Establishing a forum/community for healthcare professionals (HCPs) and authorities** to develop new guidelines and standards.

Dissemination efforts will be implemented along with the first scientific results and carried on throughout the entire project duration. The dissemination plan will largely rely on existing consortium partners' contact research and business networks expanding to industry, healthcare and technology organisations, patient associations and non-profits, and regulatory authorities and standards committees.

Communication activities started right after the project kick-off and will be carried throughout its lifetime. Activities will support dissemination and outreach objectives while targeting society at large, including citizens, patients, associations, HCPs, relevant R&I projects and policymakers at EU, national levels, and worldwide. The communication of AI-PROGNOSIS aims to be strategically planned, to identify and set clear communication objectives and to use pertinent messages, the right medium and means.

2.2 Stakeholder analysis

The success of the AI-PROGNOSIS project relies on effectively engaging a diverse range of stakeholders. These stakeholders stand to benefit from the project's outcomes and can play a pivotal role in shaping its overall impact.

The dissemination and communication actions target all involved, interested, and potential audiences to increase the impact of the different dimensions of the project. Based on the AI-PROGNOSIS project goals, the list of stakeholders (see **Table 1**) has been identified and will be reached via different dissemination and communication tools and channels. A diverse approach will be taken to engage these audiences and effectively communicate the project's goals and progress.

The main stakeholder's groups of the AI-PROGNOSIS are:

- **Persons with PD, their families, carers, and associations;**
- **The relevant primary/secondary HCPs;**

- **The relevant scientific and technical community, i.e., clinical, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and ethics research scientists and designers/developers of human-centred health technologies;**
- **The relevant industry leaders, e.g., mobile health (mHealth), medical AI, and pharma;**
- **The healthcare enablers and policymakers; and**
- **The public at large.**

Different dissemination and communication objectives are set for each stakeholder group, such as sharing scientific findings with researchers, collecting feedback from HCPs, engaging with industry partners to promote project vision, and fostering a PD-centred community among end users. The different dissemination and communication channels, including scientific conferences, publications, events, demo sessions, newsletters, social media, the project website, and major media, are foreseen to reach various target audiences. This multi-faceted approach ensures that the project's goals and progress are effectively communicated to a broad and diverse audience.

Table 1 Stakeholder groups

Main stakeholder groups	Stakeholder audience	Objectives	Dissemination & communication channels
Scientific community	Clinical, AI and ethics research scientists and designers/developers of human-centred health technologies	Communicate scientific findings and collect feedback; Transfer knowledge; Get support from the scientific community; Boost the project sustainability through the development of new related research projects; Extend network	Scientific conference presentations/posters; Publications in peer-reviewed journals; Events; Workshops; Special sessions; Seminars
Clinicians	Relevant primary/secondary health care professionals	Communicate scientific findings and collect feedback; Extend network; Communicate project progress and raise awareness regarding AI-PROGNOSIS solutions	Events; Workshops; Special sessions; Seminars
Industry	mHealth, medical AI, and pharmaceutical industry	Inform the industry about the project's vision and exchange ideas; Extend network; Demonstrate the business potential; push towards adoption of AI-PROGNOSIS	Business/Industry events and EXPOs stands/booths; Publication in business magazines; Demo sessions for stakeholders

		products and services; Collect feedback on expectations and requirements to adjust commercial exploitation plans; Emphasise the technical feasibility and competitiveness of concept and tools developed	
End users	Persons with PD, their families, carers, and associations	Project involvement; Support engagement of the participants in the studies; Build a PD-centred community; Communicate project progress and raise awareness regarding AI-PROGNOSIS solutions	Demo sessions; Newsletters; Social media; Website; Major media presence
Policymakers	This is a wide group encompassing innovation driven local, regional, national authorities, representatives & associations, Ministries, parliaments and national & international Public Administrations	Project involvement; Attract the interest of relevant stakeholders	Website; Social media; Newsletters; Major media presence; Demo sessions
General public	The general public consists of a general audience and other actors not identified as direct targeted groups by the project, though this group can have strong interest in the project: citizen Interest Groups, NGOs, Community Action Groups	General awareness; Project progress	Website; Social media; Newsletters; Major media presence

To reach out to the largest possible audience, the AI-PROGNOSIS partners will also use their own network of contacts at the local, national, European and international levels (see **Table 2**). This list will be continuously updated during the whole duration of the project.

Table 2 List of research and business networks

Category	Relevant Network/Association
Industry	Pharmaceutical: European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industry Associations; Farmaindustria; AbbVie; Roche; Biogen; Novartis;

Category	Relevant Network/Association
	Johnson&Johnson; Lilly; Merck; UCB; Pfizer; Zambon; Italfarmaco; Biowise Pharmaceuticals; Bial. MedTech/Clinical Research: Boston Scientific; Medtronic; IBM; General Electric; ICON plc; Parexel; IQVIA; PricewaterhouseCoopers; Philips Medical Systems, IEEE Society. Entrepreneurship: F6S Network; Mubadala Investment Company.
Healthcare organisations	Medical Societies: International Parkinson and Movement Disorders Society; European Academy of Neurology; American Academy of Neurology; International Association of Parkinsonism and Related Disorders; Sociedad Española de Neurología; Asociación Madrileña de Neurología; Royal College of Physicians of Cádiz; Professional Association of German neurologists; German Society for Neurology; German Society for Psychiatry and Psychotherapy, Psychosomatics and Neurology; European Hospital and Healthcare Federation; European Society of Human Genetics; American Society of Human Genetics; Cyprus Society of Human Genetics; Federation of European Neuroscience Societies; The European Network for the Cure of ALS (ENCALS); COST – the role of Immunity in tackling Parkinson’s Disease through a Translation Network; European Reference Network – Neurological Diseases (ERN-RND); European Reference Network – Neuromuscular Diseases (ERN-NMD); BBMRI-ERIC; International Association of Bioethics (IAB); World Parkinson Coalition; Dutch Parkinson Societists; Neuromod+; International Neuroethics Society Hospitals/practices: NTD network of neurologists; Charite Hospital; Humanitas; Vilnius University Hospital Santaros Klinikos; Hospital of Lithuanian University of Health Sciences Kaunas Clinics; Clinical Hospital Centre Rijeka; Geriatric Health Care Centres Graz.
Technology organisations	European Institute of Innovation and Technology Health; The European Institute for Innovation through Health Data; European Alliance for Medical and Biological Engineering & Science; International Federation for Medical and Biological Engineering; European Federation for Medical Informatics Association; Flanders AI research community.

Recognising that communication is a two-way process, great importance will be placed on listening to the needs and feedback of each target audience. This collaborative approach will allow us to refine and improve the AI-PROGNOSIS communication and dissemination activities continually.

2.3 Dissemination and communication approach

The AI-PROGNOSIS dissemination and communication approach is designed to be a dynamic and flexible process, allowing for adjustments based on feedback from various information providers, including consortium members and stakeholders. This adaptive approach considers diverse opportunities and is committed to regular reviews. The consortium will assess the effectiveness of the dissemination and communication strategy, making adjustments in response to stakeholders' needs, requirements, and the evolving progress of the project.

Key features and corresponding descriptions follow:

- Multi-faceted strategy.** A strategy encompassing traditional academic channels and innovative communication methods will be adopted. A balance between scientific rigor and accessibility will ensure that project outcomes are effectively communicated and reach a diverse audience for maximum impact.

- **Stakeholder tailoring.** Tailor messages for specific stakeholder groups, including HCPs, policymakers, patients, and the scientific community.
- **Consistency and coherence.** Ensuring messaging consistency across different channels will maintain a strong and unified project image.
- **Diverse dissemination and communication channels.** Utilising a mix of traditional and digital channels for diverse reach. Leveraging publications, participation in events, adopting open science practices, and utilising social media platforms, the project website, and newsletters will maintain consistent communication.
- **Interactive elements.** Incorporation of interactive elements in communication materials, such as infographics and interactive web content, to enhance engagement.
- **Synergies and networking.** Exploring opportunities for synergies and joint activities to expand the project's reach.
- **Adaptability.** Staying agile¹ and adapting dissemination and communication strategies based on project developments and stakeholder feedback. Conducting periodic reviews to assess the effectiveness of the communication approach and make adjustments as necessary.
- **Measurable and traceable.** The dissemination and communication approach adopted is measurable and traceable by tracking the dissemination progress.

The overall dissemination and communication approach will be based on the following pathways:

1. **Publications** in peer-reviewed journals and business magazines;
2. **Dissemination events**, such as clinical, research and business conferences, workshops, special sessions, seminars and demo sessions to stakeholders;
3. **Media presence**, such as newsletters, website/blog, social media posts or local/national major media (TV and radio) presentations;
4. **PD educational content development**, such as tailored articles, including multimedia;
5. **Synergy and networking**, such as campaigns and organisation of/participation in events;
6. **Formulation of diversified messages, languages, and content** for different target audiences;
7. **Conception and design of a coherent project branding** to achieve an effective visual identity, including logo, infographics, and banners. Acknowledgements of EU funding, to be included in all materials relevant to communication, dissemination, Intellectual property rights (IPR) and major results;
8. **Set up of different communication channels:** the project website and social media accounts to be populated with project news and achievements, further contributing to the growth of its communities of interest and an open access publication archive within the Zenodo OpenAIRE public repository;
9. **Preparation of diversified communication materials:** print-based (e.g., brochures, posters), multimedia (e.g., photos, teaser videos, interviews, demos), to be spread through website and social media.

¹ Tessarolo, Francesco, et al. "Developing ambient assisted living technologies exploiting potential of user-centred co-creation and agile methodology: The CAPTAIN project experience." *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing* (2022): 1-16.

This comprehensive and adaptive approach aims to strategically engage stakeholders, effectively convey project objectives, and ensure broad and impactful dissemination of the AI-PROGNOSIS project achievements while adhering to Open Science principles.

2.4 Dissemination activities and channels

2.4.1 Scientific publications

The AI-PROGNOSIS project is expected to develop a significant amount of research results, which will be disseminated to different key scientific communities. To maximise visibility, project partners will dedicate strong efforts to publishing scientific papers in globally recognised scientific journals that have a high-impact index and Green or Gold open access.

The AI-PROGNOSIS website will include articles summarising the scientific publications. The Open Research Europe platform will be leveraged, supporting openness in all stages of a publication's life cycle.

The project aims to publish at least **twenty (20) scientific publications** targeting Q1 journals or above to communicate scientific findings.

2.4.2 Scientific conferences

Participation in scientific conferences is an important component of the AI-PROGNOSIS project's dissemination and communication strategy. These events serve as platforms for engaging with the academic and scientific community, presenting research findings, and gathering valuable feedback. The main objectives of the AI-PROGNOSIS project's participation in scientific conferences are:

- **Communicating Scientific Findings:** Scientific conferences provide a forum to share the project's research outcomes, insights, and discoveries with peers and experts in relevant fields.
- **Feedback and Collaboration:** These events facilitate an exchange of ideas and feedback, enabling the project to benefit from the collective knowledge and expertise of the scientific community. They also offer opportunities for potential collaborations with other researchers and projects, which can further enrich the AI-PROGNOSIS initiative.

The AI-PROGNOSIS project is committed to participating in **at least twenty (20) scientific conferences**, emphasising the importance of engaging with the academic community and sharing scientific insights. The preliminary list of scientific conferences is provided in **Appendix I List of events and conferences**.

By actively participating in scientific conferences, the project aims to enhance its visibility, foster collaboration, and actively contribute to the advancement of knowledge in the field of predictive healthcare and AI.

2.4.3 Open science practices

AI-PROGNOSIS supports the Open Science approach and recognises the importance of making scientific research and its dissemination accessible to any individual of an inquiring society, from professionals to citizens. To deliver trustworthy, transparent AI tools, the project will follow a set of practices to ensure rapid and broad access to its research methods, data, and outcomes.

The project will ensure open access, with free-of-charge online access for any user to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. Furthermore, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) will specifically refer to the support of the EC.

To uphold transparency at all stages of the scientific publication life cycle, AI-PROGNOSIS will utilise the Open Research Europe² platform. Research teams will also target scientific journals with high-impact factors and Green or Gold open access to maximise visibility.

The project will provide access to at least the research datasets it generated for developing/validating its AI models and digital biomarkers (dBM)s through FAIR³ management and sharing. Other diverse research assets, such as clinical study protocols, design reports, and algorithms, are also critical to ensure reliability and reproducibility. Therefore, actions will be taken to provide timely access to them.

Study protocols will be registered early in ClinicalTrials.gov or the ISRCTN registry. Data analysis algorithms and machine learning (ML) workflows will be uploaded with appropriate licenses (subject to IPR) to open repositories, e.g., GitHub. Co-creation and design sprint reports will be accessible via research portals like Zenodo⁴. Furthermore, to translate the needs of relevant end users into its products and foster uptake, the project will also adopt citizen science concepts by enabling end-users to shape research questions underlying the development of the AI models through its co-creation process. The material used in the co-creation process, including presentations, questionnaires, and designs, will also be published.

AI-PROGNOSIS also aspires to share genetic material and expose genetic analysis processes from the AI-PRA and AI-PMP studies. The feasibility and conditions under which a third-party researcher will be able to investigate the material will be determined over the course of the project.

Data and other digital research outputs generated and shared by the project will be managed using trusted European Open Science Cloud tools, such as the Zenodo repository, ensuring full compliance with the FAIR requirements. Measures, including provisions for explicit consent from study participants, to facilitate open access to data collected within the project will be introduced as early as possible while adhering to strict GDPR compliance.

To foster reusability, open data and research outputs will be released under the Creative Commons CC BY license. The project has dedicated substantial effort to data harmonisation, employing established healthcare data standards like FHIR or OMOP, ensuring interoperability of the released data and predictive models. While opening the unified datasets used for predictive model development will be subject to the underlying licenses and data use agreements of the individual third-party databases and biobanks, the project will publish the methodology and common data model, and open source the code for dataset harmonisation, thereby enabling the process reproduction by third parties.

2.5 Communication activities and channels

2.5.1 Communication messages

Communication messages form the foundation of the AI-PROGNOSIS dissemination and communication strategy. The project's key messages (see **Table 3**) are designed to raise awareness and engagement among end users, expand the network, foster a community centred around PD, disseminate scientific findings, and keep stakeholders informed about the project's progress. These messages are versatile and adaptable, allowing the consortium to tailor project communication to the specific needs and interests of different stakeholder groups at various stages of the project. This flexibility ensures that the project mission is

² Open Research Europe - Open Access Publishing Platform <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

³ FAIR stands for: Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/>

communicated clearly and the target audiences are engaged in a way that resonates with their unique concerns and expectations.

Table 3 Communication messages and channels

Objective/ Message to communicate	Communication channel	Level	Main target audience
End user awareness and engagement	Social media; Major media presence; Newsletters; Demo sessions	National, EU	End users
Extending network	Conferences; Business events; Workshops; Special sessions; Seminars	EU, Worldwide	Academia Clinicians Industry
Building a PD-centred community	Social media; Newsletter; Mailing list; Virtual space/rooms; Conferences/events	EU, Worldwide	All audiences
Dissemination of scientific results	Publications; Conferences posters/presentations Workshops; Special sessions	Worldwide	Academia, Industry
Project progress	Website; social media; Newsletters; Major media presence	National, EU, Worldwide	All audiences

These communication messages are fundamental to the project's dissemination and communication strategy and ensure that the project mission, activities, and goals are communicated consistently and effectively to diverse audiences.

2.5.2 Publications in media outlets

While scientific publications are essential for sharing detailed research findings with the academic community, the AI-PROGNOSIS project recognises the importance of disseminating its vision and research findings to a broader audience and making the project's findings accessible beyond academia.

This outreach will include publishing at least **four (4) articles in business magazines** aimed at informing industries such as medical devices and pharmaceuticals about the project's vision. The articles published in business magazines will be presented on the website, summarising key insights.

2.5.3 Events

Events play a pivotal role in AI-PROGNOSIS's dissemination and communication strategy, serving as dynamic platforms for connecting with a wide range of stakeholders, including the general public and industry experts. These gatherings offer a unique opportunity to showcase the progress and results of the project and encourage networking. Events also supply the content to the communication channels and tools (e.g., website, social media, newsletters), greatly impacting diverse audiences.

The partners' participation in events will generate more visibility for the AI-PROGNOSIS project and will boost contact with stakeholders and other European projects.

The strategy of participation in events will be set up at three different levels in particular:

- **Business/industry events** to inform the industry about the project's vision and exchange ideas;
- **Workshops/special sessions/seminars** to communicate scientific findings and take feedback; and
- **Demo sessions for stakeholders** to increase awareness regarding the AI-PROGNOSIS solutions.

It is expected the project partners will participate in at least **three (3) business/industry events, eight (8) workshops/sessions/seminars, and organise six (6) demo sessions** for stakeholders.

Project partners have identified a preliminary list of relevant events where participation in representing the project may be planned (see **Appendix I List of events and conferences**). This list will be updated throughout the duration of the project.

The participation in events will be made visible through the AI-PROGNOSIS website and social media channels, contributing to increasing the community of stakeholders and public interest in the project.

2.5.4 Events organised by the project

In addition to participating in scientific conferences and events, the AI-PROGNOSIS project will take a proactive role in organising and hosting events. These internally organised events serve as a valuable platform for direct project-led engagement with stakeholders, enabling the project to disseminate its research findings, foster collaboration, and showcase its innovative solutions. The events also contribute to the content stream of the project's communication channels and tools, amplifying their impact across diverse audiences.

The project's strategy for organising events is designed to encompass diverse formats that cater to different purposes and audiences:

- **Plenary meetings:** These workshops are strategically organised to coincide with significant project milestones. They are forums for project partners to discuss achievements, challenges, and research results, fostering critical feedback and collaboration.
- **Virtual conferences:** The AI-PROGNOSIS may host virtual conferences that bring together a broader audience to explore topics related to the project's goals and scientific findings.
- **Specialised events:** The project partners may organise specialised events tailored to specific audiences and themes. These include significant numbers of patient and next of kin events, health data events, biobanking events, and ethics events. These events serve to engage different stakeholders, promote ethical and responsible research, and provide valuable insights into the ethical considerations of the project's work. Specialised events may be conducted either face-to-face or online.

Internally organised events (see **Appendix I List of events and conferences**) are integral to the project's outreach and engagement strategy, providing valuable touchpoints for knowledge exchange, networking, and collective progress.

2.5.5 Communication tools

The tools regarding communication of the AI-PROGNOSIS project are briefly described hereunder. However, the complete deliverable D6.1, "Project branding and communication kit", details their development and means of use.

Project brand identity. The AI-PROGNOSIS project's brand identity is defined by its minimalist yet distinctive logo and a standardised colour palette (see **Figure 2**). The logo, represented in various variations, including standard, monochromic blue and monochromic white versions, was designed to communicate several aspects of the project, including project identity, title and distinctiveness in a visually attractive, unique, and recognisable form. The colour palette corresponds with the colours featured in the project's logo and is consistently applied across project materials for brand recognition.

Figure 2 AI-PROGNOSIS main logo

Project website. The project's website, www.ai-prognosis.eu, is available from M3 and is a central hub for online communications. It aims to present the project to external stakeholders, connect with interested parties, share project progress, and provide access to dissemination materials. The website's structure includes different sections such as Home, About, Research&Development, Knowledge Base, and Newsroom, offering comprehensive information about the project's vision, objectives, research, and consortium. It is designed to be engaging, informative, and flexible, with regular updates.

All partners will contribute to website updates with information about the project's progress, related news, and events in their field of expertise.

The AI-PROGNOSIS project's website visitors' engagement is increasing. Since its launch, the website has recorded 226 visits and accumulated 1,014 page views (see **Figure 3**). On average, new visitors spend around seven minutes per visit, while returning visitors show higher engagement, with an average visit duration of 29 minutes and 22 seconds. This increasing trend in visitor interaction reflects a growing interest in the website's content and the project as a whole.

Figure 3 AI-PROGNOSIS's website traffic overview

Social media channels. Social media channels are essential for communicating and disseminating the project’s activities and outcomes and engaging with the public. They serve as effective tools to increase the visibility of the project results within the stakeholders’ community.

AI-PROGNOSIS maintains active profiles on LinkedIn, X (formerly Twitter), and Facebook (see **Table 4**), which are linked to the AI-PROGNOSIS website. These platforms are regularly utilised to promote the project's activities and outputs. All project partners are encouraged to share relevant project information through these channels.

Table 4 AI-PROGNOSIS social media channels

Social media channel	AI-PROGNOSIS handle in the channel
LinkedIn	@ai-prognosis
X (former Twitter)	@aiprognois
Facebook	AI-PROGNOSIS

Social media channels are active from M1. As of the preparation of D6.2, the number of social media followers was as follows: LinkedIn – 199 (see **Figure 4**), X (former Twitter) – 31 (see **Figure 5**), and Facebook – 15 followers.

Figure 4 Follower metrics on LinkedIn

During the 91 days period X (formerly Twitter), AI-PROGNOSIS Tweets accumulated a total of 2.7 impressions, averaging 30 impressions per day, reflecting the results of the engagement and reach of AI-PROGNOSIS content (see **Figure 5**).

Figure 5 Followers and Tweet activity metrics on X (former Twitter)

Communication kit. The communication kit includes materials for print, digital items (web banners), and document and presentation templates. These materials maintain a consistent visual identity for the project and support communication and dissemination activities.

At the beginning of the project, in months 1-3, project poster, flyer and roll-up banner were developed. These items reflect the project's brand and provide an overview of the essential information about the project. The stakeholders and interested parties can easily access and download these materials from the project's website for the purpose of promoting or representing the project. The communication kit is currently available in English. However, the project consortium is aware that translations into additional languages may become necessary to reach a broader audience as the project progresses.

Dedicated banners have been designed for all AI-PROGNOSIS social media profiles to ensure a consistent appearance. The banners incorporate the project's colour palette, ensuring visual consistency with the overall brand style. Harmonisation across all platforms ensures project recognisability and a professional project presentation. The project aims to create a more memorable and engaging online presence by presenting a visually cohesive identity, thus promoting effective engagement and communication with the audience.

In addition, three essential templates, i.e., Deliverable, Meeting Minute, and Presentation templates, were designed to enhance the project management, reporting and communication within the consortium and maintain consistency in the project's deliverables, meeting documentation, and presentations.

Newsletter. The newsletter will be issued quarterly, starting from M4. It will contain a summary of the latest news about the project, the latest scientific publications related to the project, and information about the project events.

The newsletter will be available in PDF format which is suitable for online and offline communication and dissemination activities. The content will be presented in accessible language, designed for the general public, and will cover the following topics:

- Project progress and updates on project development;
- Latest project-related publications highlighting the most recent research findings;
- Project events, conferences, and meetings where AI-PROGNOSIS is presented;
- Interviews with project partners on the latest activities and achievements; and
- Information about interesting activities and new initiatives related to the project.

The newsletter will be promoted on the project's social media channels and website and made available through the Zenodo public repository, ensuring broad accessibility and dissemination.

In summary, AI-PROGNOSIS will rely on clear branding, an informative website, and active social media engagement to effectively communicate its achievements and engage with stakeholders.

2.5.6 PD educational content development

The purpose of the educational content development is to create engaging and interactive materials that raise awareness about PD and improve health literacy. The content aims to reach both individuals with PD and those without it. The focus will be on providing valuable insights into the benefits of early detection, sharing experiences from both patients and HCPs. Content may include, for example, exploring the role of new technologies and AI and describing actionable factors and lifestyle choices that can slow down the progression and positively impact the quality of life.

The planned content formats for educational materials include:

- **Tailored articles:** In-depth articles on various aspects of PD, written in an accessible and informative style.
- **Multimedia:** Infographics, charts, and visual representations to simplify complex information and make it more accessible.

Educational content will be developed in close collaboration clinical partners to ensure accuracy and relevance. Utilising contemporary tools like Mentimeter⁵ and Genially⁶, will ensure content is visually engaging and interactive.

Educational material will be disseminated through various channels, more specifically:

- **mAI-Health/Care Apps:** A dedicated section within the apps to provide easy access to educational content for users.
- **Project Website:** A comprehensive section on the website where all educational materials can be accessed.
- **Social Media:** Regular posts on social media platforms to reach and engage a wider audience.
- **Newsletters:** Inclusion of educational content in newsletters targeting project stakeholders.

⁵ <https://www.mentimeter.com/>

⁶ <https://genial.ly/>

- **Potentially other popular publications:** Collaborations with popular publications to feature content in easily accessible formats will be explored.

By following this comprehensive plan, the educational content aims to raise PD awareness effectively, contribute to health literacy, and empower individuals to make informed decisions about PD. The combination of tailored articles and multimedia content, developed in collaboration with clinical partners and utilising contemporary tools, will ensure the delivery of engaging and accurate information across multiple platforms.

2.6 Clustering and networking activities

As part of T6.2, the project partners will undertake clustering and networking activities focusing on raising awareness, exchanging knowledge and communicating the project vision and outcomes to key stakeholder groups (e.g., policy formulators, decision-makers, HCPs, PD organisations, private companies).

EU projects and initiatives that are considered more relevant for the AI-PROGNOSIS in the field to establish an ecosystem of collaboration through which experience, materials and results will be exchanged to stimulate mutual growth have been shortlisted (see **Table 5**), including the so-called “sister projects“ that have been funded by the European Commission under the same HORIZON-HLTH-2022-STAYHLTH-01-04-two-stage call. Outreach activities to create synergies with sister projects and maximise the project’s impact are planned for Y1. This list will be updated throughout the project.

In early October 2023, the AI-PROGNOSIS project began collaborating and creating synergy with the Digital Health Uptake (DHU) project. This collaboration involves mutually promoting relevant news and events through project websites, newsletters, and social media channels. Additionally, the possibility of co-organising events together is being explored.

Table 5 Preliminary list of R&I projects, initiatives for clustering and networking

Project Acronym	Title
SmartCHANGE	AI-based long-term health risk evaluation for driving behaviour change strategies in children and youth
TRUSTroke	Trustworthy AI for improvement of stroke outcomes
VASCUL-AID	Developing trustworthy artificial intelligence (AI)-driven tools to predict vascular disease risk and progression
ARTILLERY	Artificial Intelligence for early detection of non-communicable disease risk in people with breast cancer
AI4HF	Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence for Personalised Risk Assessment in Chronic Heart Failure
AI-POD	Trustworthy AI Tools for the Prediction of Obesity Related Vascular Diseases
STRATIFYHF	Artificial intelligence-based decision support system for risk stratification and early detection of heart failure in primary and secondary care
TRUSTING	A Trustworthy speech-based AI monitoring system for the prediction of relapse in individuals with schizophrenia
Digital Health Uptake (DHU) project	The European project funded through the Digital Europe Programme that aims to facilitate the alignment of policies, strategies, instruments and activities to advance the uptake of digital health solutions and

Project Acronym	Title
	services in Europe. The work of DHU is grouped under three key aspects: RADAR, KNOWLEDGE COMMUNITY and ACCELERATOR
iPROLEPSIS	Psoriatic arthritis inflammation explained through multi-source data analysis guiding a novel personalised digital care ecosystem
iCARE-PD	iCare-PD is a project that is dedicated to address complex care in PD by developing and implementing an integrated care delivery model across various countries
DIOPTRA	Colorectal cancer (CRC) risk assessment, screening, and progression

Other initiatives considered for networking and clustering follow:

- Participatory eHealth & Health data Research Group (PeHR) supporting the continuous transformation of healthcare in Sweden and internationally through participatory research on eHealth and health data;
- HSG's Genetics Working Group, the world's first HD cooperative therapeutic research organisation, facilitating high-quality clinical research trials and studies that bring closer to finding more effective treatments for Huntington's disease (HD) and reducing the burden of HD for families affected by the disease; and
- Health Data Sweden, the one-stop-shop for the acceleration of digital transformation in health data for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and the public sector, through the use of key technologies.

The collaboration with these projects will happen on several levels including, but not limited to:

- Co-organisation of events;
- Exchange of information related to project achievements;
- Mutual promotion: dissemination and communication using social media and online presence tools; and
- Participation in AI-PROGNOSIS events and vice versa.

The AI-PROGNOSIS project is committed to participating in/organising no less than **four (4) networking/joint initiatives**.

Towards the end of the project, a large clustering workshop will be organised to demonstrate the final and validated version of the digital health ecosystem to representatives of key stakeholder groups.

2.7 Dissemination and communication guidelines

2.7.1 Roles and responsibilities per partner

This section outlines the individual plans for communication and dissemination of each project partner (see **Table 6**), showcasing their strategies for sharing project developments and research findings.

Table 6 Individual plans for dissemination and communication

Partner	Individual plans for communication and dissemination
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH)	AUTH will execute a comprehensive dissemination and communication plan to share the research findings produced within the AI-PROGNOSIS framework. This plan includes various dissemination activities such as journal publications, international conferences, workshops, EU-focused events, and technical/academic events, along with communication activities like social media posts, website blog/news posts, press releases/newsletters, traditional media, and interactive face-to-face networking.
Ainigma Technologies (AING)	AING will focus on showcasing project updates and milestones via participation in international conferences, workshops and events and via social media platforms.
Netcompany-Intrasoft (INTRA)	INTRA's dissemination and communication strategy includes sharing project updates and research through journal publications, international conferences, technical events, EU-focused events, social media, and blog articles.
Diadikasia Business Consulting (DBC)	DBC will disseminate and communicate project outcomes by leveraging on its social media.
Uppsala Universitet (UU)	UU will implement a dissemination and communication plan that encompasses various activities aimed at spreading the research findings generated within the AI-PROGNOSIS framework. These activities involve journal publications, international conferences, workshops, EU-focused events, technical/academic events, as well as communication activities such as social media posts, website blog/news posts, press releases/newsletters, traditional media, interactive face-to-face networking, and newsletters for both individual and organisational recipients.
Abbvie Deutschland GmbH & CO KG (ABBV)	ABBV will disseminate and communicate project outcomes by leveraging on its social media.
Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Toulouse (CHUT)	CHUT will engage in dissemination activities mainly through journal publications and participation in international conferences.
Faculdade de Motricidade Humana (FMH-ULisboa)	FMH-ULisboa will engage in dissemination through journal publications, international conferences, and academic events, while their communication activities will include social media posts, website blog/news posts, traditional media, and interactive face-to-face networking.
Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH)	CERTH will engage in dissemination activities mainly through journal publications.
Neurotransdata GMBH (NTD)	NTD's dissemination and communication activities include hosting internal events and distributing an internal newsletter tailored for shareholders.
Katholieke Universiteit Leuven (KUL)	KUL's dissemination and communication activities consist of journal publications, conferences, workshops, EU-focused events, technical/academic events, social media posts, press releases/newsletters, and interactive face-to-face networking.
SQUAREDEV (SQD)	SQD will disseminate and communicate project outcomes by leveraging its social media.
Technische Universitaet Dresden (TUD)	TUD will disseminate and communicate project outcomes leveraging its social media.
SMARTSOL (SSOL)	SSOL will ensure effective communication by showcasing project results and findings on the official website and social media.

Partner	Individual plans for communication and dissemination
The Cyprus Institute of Neurology & Genetics (CING)	CING's dissemination activities for the AI-PROGNOSIS include journal publications, international conferences, workshops, EU-focused events, and technical/academic events. They will also engage in communication activities like social media posts, website blog/news posts, press releases/newsletters, traditional media, and interactive face-to-face networking.
Fundacion Iniciativa para las Neurociencias - Foundation for Initiatives in Neuroscience (FIN)	FIN's dissemination and communication activities for the AI-PROGNOSIS encompass journal publications, international conferences, social media posts, website blogs, press releases, and interactive face-to-face networking.
King's College London (KCL)	KCL will disseminate and communicate project outcomes by leveraging its social media.
The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of The University of Oxford (UOXF)	UOXF will engage in various dissemination and communication activities, including journal publications, international conferences, workshops, EU-focused events, technical/academic events, social media posts, and interactive face-to-face networking as part of the AI-PROGNOSIS project.

2.7.2 Usage of language

Categorising audiences has a real impact on what communication the project produces and how it is written, designed and distributed. For example:

- **Language style:** The tone and language used in communication will vary based on the audience's level of expertise. Technical communication, therefore, has its place, but not in dissemination and communication content written for the public community (unless requested). Furthermore, positive language and figurative language⁷ will be integrated into AI-PROGNOSIS communication. This approach will help to consider diverse perspectives in a positive manner and in a way that adapts to people with PD.
- **Design style:** This is equally true for design issues. In essence, it may be counter-productive and a waste of resources to design a report aimed at highly specialised audiences as a glossy product covered with a multitude of images and illustrations. In this case, the product type is inappropriate for both the audience and the message.

For each audience, the following questions will be addressed, and the language of messages will be adapted:

- Why do they need to know?
- What makes the issue urgent?
- What are the consequences if no action is taken?
- What solutions is AI-PROGNOSIS offering?
- How does AI-PROGNOSIS work relate to everyday life?
- Is AI-PROGNOSIS linked to any broader societal issue?

Rather than focusing only on providing factual information, the project consortium will position the research topic within a broader socio-economic and policy context so that it will be easier to explain the results and their relevance to policymakers and the general public. Additionally, adopting positive and figurative language not only enhances the accessibility of the project's

⁷ Use of Figurative Language by People With Parkinson Disease to Describe "Off" Periods | Neurology Clinical Practice

messages but also aligns with a commitment to fostering understanding and engagement among diverse audiences, especially among people with PD.

2.7.3 Prior notice of scientific publications

The AI-PROGNOSIS project partners must disseminate their results as soon as feasible, in a publicly available format, subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate interests.

A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give at least 45 (forty-five) calendar days advance notice to the other beneficiaries, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

Any other beneficiary may object within 30 (thirty) calendar days of receiving notification if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests.

2.7.4 Acknowledgment of funding and disclaimer

Communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, and presentations, in electronic form, via traditional or social media), dissemination activities and/or major result must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate) (see **Figure 6**).

Figure 6 EU logo

The European Commission's support of the AI-PROGNOSIS project must be acknowledged in all the dissemination and communication tools and materials, including the following disclaimer:

"Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the European Health and Digital Executive Agency can be held responsible for them."

The EU logo and acknowledgment of the EU support will be stored and made easily accessible to all project partners on the project's SharePoint platform.

2.8 Dissemination and communication impact assessment

2.8.1 Key Performance Indicators

Monitoring the impact of the different dissemination and communication activities implies a systematic collection of data and reporting of information from all partners. This information is needed to assess the success of the dissemination and communication strategy.

The communication and dissemination objectives will be reached through the activities of all partners: individually, through each partner's entity activities, and collectively, through the

partner's contribution to the global strategy with the goal to reach the stakeholders of the project and build the AI-PROGNOSIS community.

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been defined to measure the impact of each dissemination and communication activity (see **Table 7**). KPIs will be used throughout the project, and the dissemination and communication strategy will be adjusted if KPIs and the desired impact are not achieved.

Table 7 KPIs table

Dissemination and communication actions	What	When	Key Performance Indicators
Publications	Peer-reviewed journals	From M18, when solid scientific results are available	20 publications
	Business Magazines		4 publications
Dissemination events	Scientific conference presentations/ posters	From M12, when initial scientific results are available	20 presentations/posters
	Business/Industry events, and EXPOs stands/booths		3 events
	Workshops/ Special sessions/ Seminars	From M18, when solid scientific results are available	8 events 50 expected attendees
	Demo sessions for stakeholders	From M18, when alpha versions of tools are available	6 demo sessions
Media presence	Newsletters	From M4, every quarter	1000 subscribers
	Website/blog posts	From M3	4 posts/month 1000 visitors/month
	Social media posts	From M1	2 posts/week 2000 followers
	Major media (TV/radio) presence	From M6, when tangible results will be available	5 appearances in national media 2 appearances in EU-level media
Networking and clustering events		From M6, when tangible results will be available	≥4 networking/joint initiatives

All the impacts will be compiled in three deliverables, namely: D6.3 “First report on project visibility and educational material” (month 18), D6.5 “Midterm report on project visibility and education material” (month 32), and D6.6 “Final report on project visibility and education material” at the end of the project (month 48).

2.8.2 Tracking and monitoring the activities

SMARTSOL SIA will be responsible for monitoring and tracking all the dissemination and communication activities carried out by the partners. To facilitate this process, a tracking form

(see **Table 8**) was created to collect information regarding the dissemination and communication activities undertaken by each partner, namely:

- **Publications;**
- **Event participation and organisation;**
- **Media presence; and**
- **Networking and clustering events.**

Table 8 KPIs tracking form

Dissemination pillar	No	Partner	Type of publication (Peer-reviewed journal / business magazine)	Title of journal / business magazine	Number of journal/Magazine	Type of PID (repository)	Link to publication (if no PID of publication)	Title of publication	Authors	Date when published	Notes
Publications	Publication in Peer-reviewed journals - planned to be achieved: 20 publications										
	1										
	2										
	3										
	4										
	5										
	6										
	7										
	8										
	9										
	10										
	11										
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	14										
	15										
	16										
	17										
	18										
	19										
	20										
	21										
	22										
	23										
	24										
25											
	Business Magazines - planned to be achieved: 4 publications										
	1										
	2										
	3										
	4										
	5										
	6										
	7										
	8										
	9										

The information in the tracking form will encompass project partners’ reports on dissemination and communication activities, as well as analytics by WIX to assess website reach, social media analytics, and Zenodo analytics to measure the dissemination's effectiveness.

All partners will be encouraged to consistently update this tracking form whenever they engage in any communication or dissemination actions within the AI-PROGNOSIS project.

At the end of each reporting period, this document will allow elaborate dissemination impact analysis to evaluate the impact of the actions, the type and number of people reached, and to check if the planned KPIs have been met. If not, corrective measures will be undertaken.

3 Exploitation strategy

3.1 Objectives

In alignment with the Grant Agreement, each beneficiary is obligated, up to four years after the end of the project, to take measures to ensure the exploitation of its results (either directly or indirectly, in particular through transfer or licensing).

This deliverable outlines the initial exploitation strategy, aiming to develop a comprehensive plan covering socio-economic analysis, regulatory approval, and intellectual property management. The goal is to ensure the commercialisation and applicability of the AI-PROGNOSIS outcomes beyond the project's lifespan. Additionally, the impact assessment

distinguishes between short-term exploitation and long-lasting impact while leveraging EC services to support effective dissemination and maximise societal benefits.

Key components include:

- **Exploitation plan**, including in-depth socio-economic and market analysis, focusing on technological solutions for PD diagnosis and management. The plan envisages the identification of exploitable outcomes and the development of joint exploitation schemes, including detailed business plans and cost-effectiveness evaluation using tools like Monitoring and Assessment Framework for the European Innovation Partnership on Active and Healthy Ageing (MAFEIP)⁸.
- **IPR management** aimed at managing ownership and access to knowledge (IPR, data, software, etc.), which is of utmost importance to ensure the proper exploitation of the work and its outcomes for both individual project partners and the consortium as a whole.
- **Regulatory approval plan** aimed at defining requirements and roadmap for the AI-PROGNOSIS digital care tools to achieve CE certification/MHRA approval within five years post-project and outline requirements for other countries (e.g., FDA clearance) through liaison with relevant regulatory bodies.

3.2 Exploitation plan and IP management outline

This section details specific actions to transform the project's outputs into exploitable products and services, ensuring the continuity and sustainability of the initiative. The exploitation strategy and intellectual property (IP) management throughout the project will focus on three main pillars in particular:

- **Specifying Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and evaluating their exploitation and innovation potential.**
- **Defining target stakeholders, markets, clients, and users.**
- **Identifying the most appropriate IPR strategies and business plans for the innovations.**

Detailed information on KERs, including ownership, type, exploitation goals, and the anticipated time to market or maturity, is presented in **Table 9**.

Table 9 Key exploitable results and exploitation goals

KER	Ownership (Individual/Joint)	Type	Exploitation goal	Time to market/ Maturity time
Datasets	Joint	Open access, Usage rights	New projects, Publications	1-2 years
AI models/ digital biomarkers	Individual/Joint	Commercial, Usage rights	Spin-off, New projects, Publications	1-3 years
SW apps (mAI-Health/ Care/Insights)/ HW components	Individual	Commercial	Spin-off, Revenue	2-4 years

⁸ <https://digitalhealthurope.eu/resources/mafeip/>

KER	Ownership (Individual/Joint)	Type	Exploitation goal	Time to market/ Maturity time
Integrated AI-PROGNOSIS digital	Individual/Joint	Commercial	Spin-off, Revenue	3-5 years
Clinical validation results	Individual/Joint	Non-commercial	Patents, Publications, New projects	1-3 years
Infrastructure	Individual	Commercial	Spin-off; Revenue	1-5 years
Methodology framework	Joint	Open access, Usage rights	New projects, Publications	1-3 years

Exploitation planning and IPR management activities will start early in the project and produce tangible results towards the second half of the project through a preliminary internal survey based on the EC Innovation Radar methodology⁹ to facilitate the identification and assessment of the first exploitable results.

The project will generate direct and indirect KERs, constituting the project’s value proposition.

Direct KERs include datasets, AI models, digital biomarkers, computer software (SW) applications, and an integrated digital health toolkit. Indirect KERs encompass clinical study protocols/outcomes, the infrastructure for data harmonisation, analytics, software development (CI/CD), and the overarching methodological framework, i.e., the trustworthy AI development and evaluation framework (TrustAIOps), the co-creation method, and the Data Management Plan (DMP).

The AI-PROGNOSIS main value chain (see **Figure 7**) describes the activities needed to bring the product(s) to market and shows the roles of partners and the interrelation of expected KERs.

Figure 7 AI-PROGNOSIS value proposition, KERs and main value chain

⁹ <https://innovation-radar.ec.europa.eu/methodology>

The KERs are interrelated and can be exploited as one business unit and/or separately. Individual exploitation does not only regard financing and sales but also means investing in research, i.e., increasing scientific impact, extending the network and future research funding pursuit. The pathway followed will be analysed during the project in the exploitation planning activities.

Exploitation plans will consider the key target market, which, in the case of AI-PROGNOSIS, is the “AI in Healthcare”. Other relevant markets that will be analysed include the “Silver Economy”¹⁰ and “Smart Hospitals”¹¹.

Based on consultation activities between involved partners, the leaders of the IP rights (T1.5) and exploitation-focused (T6.4) tasks, and key external stakeholders, the resulting exploitation plan will be elaborated in close cooperation with all partners and incorporating strategic feedback from external experts from industry, healthcare and academia.

Throughout the project implementation, all partners will contribute to identifying results that may qualify for IPR protection by continuous analysis of output progress within WPs, allowing rapid application to the European Patent Office (EPO) where relevant. Patenting and other protective procedures will proceed along with the regulations set forth in the Consortium Agreement on a royalty-free basis.

The exploitation methodology will be implemented during the four years of the AI-PROGNOSIS project, intensifying the efforts dedicated as soon as the results are more consistent and technologically mature.

Regarding exploitation, an in-depth socioeconomic and market analysis will be performed, focusing on the landscape of available technological solutions for PD diagnosis and management as well as the characteristics and respective needs of each potential target group. Developing a clear understanding and maintaining consistent monitoring of where the AI-PROGNOSIS stands with respect to its competitors’ actions and its potential beneficiaries’ needs early on is crucial for the efficient implementation of exploitation actions in the future. Further, in collaboration with T1.5 “Innovation and intellectual property management”, exploitable outcomes of the project will be identified, and the means for their concrete use and delivery to the market will be explored through the definition of individual exploitation plans and development of joint exploitation schemes, including detailed business plans.

The business pertaining to the joint exploitation plan will include details on the proposed management and ownership structure as well as the intellectual property elements developed throughout the project.

Finally, the cost-effectiveness of the AI-PROGNOSIS digital care tools will be evaluated using established tools, such as MAFEIP or IPscore¹², a digital tool for patent, technologies and research project evaluation, developed initially by the Danish Patent Office and offered by the European Patent Office (EPO).

In essence, exploitation, business planning and IPR management lay the foundation for meaningful and lasting impact, ensuring the continuity and sustainability of the project and will leverage consortium technological leadership and business networks in the AI and technology sector, as well as technology transfer offices of technical academic partners.

¹⁰ https://publications.europa.eu/resource/cellar/2dca9276-3ec5-11e8-b5fe-01aa75ed71a1.0002.01/DOC_1

¹¹ Smart Hospitals Market Size & Share Industry Growth 2023 - 2031 ([transparencymarketresearch.com](https://www.transparencymarketresearch.com))

¹² <https://www.epo.org/en/searching-for-patents/business/ipscore>

3.3 Impact assessment

Guided by industry and SMEs partners, the consortium will specify the exploitable assets and develop joint and individual exploitation plans based on thorough socio-economic/market analyses and agreed-on IPRs. Partners possessing expertise in the regulatory framework will develop the regulatory approval roadmap for the MVP through timely liaison with relevant bodies and close collaboration with clinical and technical partners.

Expected exploitation KPIs to be reached over the course of the project follow:

- **≥2 joint exploitation plans;**
- **≥10 individual exploitation plans; and**
- **1 regulatory approval plan.**

Reports focusing on results and activities implemented will be provided as deliverables D6.4 “Exploitation and regulatory approval plan (initial version)” (month 22), and D6.7 “Exploitation and regulatory approval plan (final version)” (month 48).

In the next step, however, the focus lies on deliberating how to generate impact through exploitation. Regarding exploitation as a proxy for impact is not correct since exploitation is a short-term effect, whereas impact is characterised as a long-lasting and observable change in/at/onto the desired object. The impact is often not predictable, as it depends on multiple variables that influence its likelihood to occur. With a view on this deliverable and considering the early stage of the project’s implementation, we provide a list of EC services to support exploitation in Horizon Europe (HORIZON) projects.

Usually, these services are free of charge for beneficiaries and are on offer for individual projects and project groups in case several projects can be accommodated under a joint topic. Depending on the type of service, these are the most common ways of support offered:

- Providing support in effective dissemination and raising the exploitation potential of research results generated, in particular, what concerns project strategies on dissemination, business plan development or going to the market;
- Providing a platform to publish and promote research results targeting a broad range of stakeholders (from business to academia); and
- Providing advice on how to spark thinking in an “innovation mindset” within a project context and support in the identification of innovation actors relevant to the project.

With a view on the consortium’s specific needs (some of which might only arise at a later stage of the project), it is important to be aware of them first. Whether the project will request support from any or more of these services remains to be seen. The consortium considers it more beneficial to access these services just in case a real need emerges from the dissemination and exploitation actions to allow to receive tailored support rather than to send very general requests without any further context.

The list of EC services supporting exploitation in Horizon Europe (HORIZON) projects includes:

1. Horizon Results Booster

Mission statement: “Horizon Results Booster – Steering research towards strong societal impact, concretising the value of R&I activity for societal challenges”.

Type: Support strategy development in dissemination and exploitation, business development and go-to-market Management: META Group with further partners.

Website: <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>

For the AI-PROGNOSIS, the following services are on offer:

- For single projects support in the exploitation of research results;
- For project groups support in disseminating research results;
- Support in the development of a business plan and attract additional funding for implementing project results after the project's end; and
- Support in preparing project results for commercialisation.

2. Innovation Radar

Mission statement: "Our goal is to allow every citizen, public official, professional and businessperson to discover the outputs of EU innovation funding and give them a chance to seek out innovators who could follow in the footsteps of companies such as Skype, TomTom, ARM Holdings, all of whom received EU funding in their early days".

Type: Providing advice on how to spark thinking in an "innovation mindset" within a project context and support in the identification of innovation actors relevant to the project; Identification of high-potential innovations and innovators in EU-funded R&I projects.

Website: <https://www.innoradar.eu/>

For AI-PROGNOSIS, the Innovation Radar might be interesting because of three main reasons, more specifically:

- To understand how real innovations emerge from EU-funded projects: What are typical patterns leading to innovations in EU-funded projects? What are drivers, enablers, obstacles?
- To get an idea of where the innovators are located and about their features on the market → Get in touch for the creation of synergies, knowledge transfer, and fostering European networks;
- To search for innovations and partners related to it in the field of PD → Get in touch for the creation of synergies, knowledge transfer, and fostering European networks.

3. Open Research Europe platform

Type: An open-access publishing platform for scientific papers for Horizon Europe (HORIZON) projects and Horizon Europe beneficiaries, including an open peer review and article.

Website: <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/for-authors/publish-your-research>

4. Horizon Results platform

Mission: "Turning Europe's research results into innovations which generate value for economy, society and contribute to a sustainable future".

Type: A platform for showcasing research results, finding collaboration opportunities and getting inspired by the results of others. Publishing results is part of the project execution for which all partners are responsible.

Website: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform>

5. European Standardisation Booster Service for EU Projects

Mission: To support EU Research and Innovation projects to valorise results through standardisation and address urgencies identified in the EU Strategy on Standardisation.

Type: Provides consultancy services to guide and support beneficiaries and consortia of R&I projects to make sure they take the right strategic approach and contribute efficiently to the Standardisation process and to make them active players in the development of Standards in the corresponding area or domain.

Website: <http://hsbooster.eu/>

6. Horizon IP Scan

Mission: Horizon IP Scan is a tailored, free-of-charge, first-line IP support service provided by the European Commission specifically designed to help European start-ups and other SMEs involved in EU-funded collaborative research projects to efficiently manage and valorise IP in collaborative R&I efforts.

The objective is to help SMEs address central IP issues that may arise at different stages of a collaborative research project.

Type: Horizon IP Scan entails three major steps:

1. a preparation phase including a pre-interview;
2. the main interview, which is done in an in-person or online meeting; and
3. and the provision of a report and recommendations.

Website: https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/services/horizon-ip-scan_en

4 Conclusions

The dissemination, communication and exploitation plan outlined in this document provides a clear roadmap for spreading awareness and promoting the outcomes of the AI-PROGNOSIS project. It gives an overview of dissemination, communication and exploitation actions planned during the project to valorise its results and bring it to the public and the market.

The plan includes a set of priorities organised into three complementary actions, namely: dissemination, communication, and exploitation. These actions ensure that the project's outputs are not only well-disseminated but also effectively exploited for long-term impact.

Overall, D6.2 outlines the strategic direction and practical steps for making the project's results effectively disseminated, reaching the intended audiences, and achieving lasting impact in the field of PD research and healthcare.

Appendix I List of events and conferences

This appendix provides a preliminary list of upcoming events and conferences in healthcare, technology, and research fields where AI-PROGNOSIS partners may plan to participate in representing the project.

Table 10 Preliminary list of events and conferences

Title of the event	Date	Link
Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC)	EMBC 2024: 15-19/7/2024	https://embc.embs.org/2024/
IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing (ICASSP)	ICASSP 2024: 14-19/4/2024	https://2024.ieeeicassp.org/
International Conference on Human Computer Interaction (HCI)	HCI 2024: 24/6-4/7/2024	https://2024.hci.international/submissions.html
Accelerating innovation for healthy ageing (AgeingFit)	2024 event: 11-12/3/2024	https://www.ageingfit-event.com/
Fostering innovation in MedTech (MedFit)	2023 event: 10-11/10/2023	https://www.medfit-event.com/
ECHAlliance Digital Health Society Summit	2023 event: 14-15/11/2023	https://echalliance.com/events-health-connector/flagship-events/5th-digital-health-society-summit/
European Health Conference & Exhibition (HIMSS)	2024 event: 29-31/5/2024	https://www.himss.org/event-himss-europe
The European Institute for Innovation through Health Data (i~HD) Annual Conference	2023 event: 29/11-1/12/2023	https://www.i-hd.eu/ac2023/
Radical Health Festival	2024 event: 22-23/5/2024	https://radicalhealthfestival.mesukeskus.com/
Digital Health World Congress	2023 event: 29-30/11/2023	https://digitalhealthcareworldcongress.com/
International Congress of Parkinson's Disease and Movement Disorders	27/9-1/10 2024	https://www.mdscongress.org/
European Academy of Neurology (EAN) Congress	June 29-July 2 2024	
International Multithematic Scientific Bio-Medical Congress (IMBMC)	2023 event: 9-11//2023	https://bsc.euc.ac.cy/
Conference of Cyprus Society of Human Genetics (CSHG)	2024 event: not confirmed	https://cshg.org.cy/
European Society of Human Genetics (ESHG)	2024 event: 01-04/06/2024	N/A
European Huntington's Disease Network (EHDN)	2024 event: 10/2024	N/A
MaxQuant Summer School 2024	N/A	N/A

Title of the event	Date	Link
Significant number of lead patient, patient, patient- and next of kin events. Health data events. Biobanking events. Ethics events.	Rolling	N/A
Significant number of lead patient, patient, patient- and next of kin events. Health data events. Biobanking events. Ethics events.	Rolling	N/A
Devoxx. Annual developers conference	Depending on the location. Various dates within the year	https://devoxx.be/
Open Data Science Conference (ODSC) 2024	N/A	https://odsc.com/europe/mlops/
Software Development Conference (QCON)	N/A	https://qconlondon.com/
ECML PKDD	Sept 22, 2023	https://sml.disi.unitn.it/hldm23
Congresso Nacional do Doente com Parkinson	April 11, 2024	
Congresso Anual da SPDMov 2024	March 15-16, 2024	https://spdmov.org/congresso-anual-da-spdmov-2024/
World Congress on Parkinson's Disease and related disorders	May 19-22, 2024	https://iaprd-parkinson.org/
Champalimaud Research Symposium (CRSy)	October, 2024	https://symposium.fchampalimaud.science/
World Congress for Neurorehabilitation (WCNR)	May 22-25, 2024	
Congress on neuroRehabilitation and Neural Repair	June, 2024	https://www.neurorehabrepair.eu/
EEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)	N/A	https://cvpr.thecvf.com/Conferences/2024
International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)	N/A	https://cvpr.thecvf.com/Conferences/2024
IEEE International Conference on Imaging systems & Techniques (IST)	N/A	https://ist2023.ieee-ims.org/
IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)	N/A	https://2024.ieeeicassp.org/
Pervasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments (PETRA)	N/A	http://www.petrae.org/index.html
Alzheimer's & Parkinson's Diseases Conference (AD/PD) 2024	March 5-9, 2024	https://adpd.kenes.com/